

TABLE—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE SPIROTHIAZOLIDINONES OF TYPE-I

Sr.	R	Formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	Dimethylformamide c(1,1)	[α] _D ²⁰ °	% of Nitrogen		Diameter of the zone of inhibition in mm		
							Found	Cal.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NOS	53	159-61	2.00	+3.5	4.5	4.62	11	10	10
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	41	152-54	3.00	+3.0	4.35	4.41	10	10	10
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	48	158-60	1.50	+2.3	4.5	4.41	14	16	17
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NOS	48	180-82	2.00	+3.5	4.45	4.41	11	14	23
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	51	108-10	2.40	+3.4	4.3	4.20	17	13	22
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	38	150-52	2.30	+2.6	4.3	4.20	15	11	10
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ NO ₂ S	60	169-71	2.00	+3.5	4.25	4.20	18	15	12
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	53	112-14	2.50	+2.4	4.1	4.15	25	14	25
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	50	172-74	2.50	+2.8	4.2	4.15	21	12	18
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ NOSCl	58	178-80	2.00	+4.0	4.2	4.15	16	13	22

Experimental

(a) Preparation of (-)-menthone⁹ :

(-)-Menthone was prepared by the oxidation of (-)-menthol [α]_D¹⁸ - 50.1° (ethanol) by potassium dichromate solution and had [α]_D²⁰ - 24.8°, d_4^{20} = 0.8954.

(b) Preparation of 1-phenylaza-4-thia-6-isopropyl-9-methylspiro[4,5]-decane-2-one :

A mixture of (-)-menthone (3.18 g; 0.02 mole), aniline (1.95 g; 0.02 mole) and anhydrous benzene (10 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 6 hrs. Thioglycolic acid (4 ml; 80%) and anhydrous sodium sulphate were then added and contents were refluxed further for 6 hrs. The product was isolated and crystallised from aqueous ethanol after the removal of benzene and unreacted thioglycolic acid, yield 52%, m.p. 159-61° (Found C = 71.0, H = 8.0, N = 4.50; C₁₈H₂₅NOS, requires C = 71.31, H = 8.25, N = 4.62).

Similarly other bases were condensed. The physical constants are recorded in Table.

Antimicrobial Screening

The purified products were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method¹⁰ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e., *Staphylococcus aureus* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e., *Escherichia coli*. The testing was carried out in DMF solution at a concentration of 10 mg/ml. The zones of inhibition of the test solution (0.5 mg) were recorded (Table). *o*- and *m*-Chlorophenylaza derivatives were highly active while *o*-anisyl, *p*-anisyl and *p*-chlorophenylaza derivatives were moderately active against *S. aureus*. *m*-Tolylaza derivative possess good activity against *E. coli* while other products were normally active.

The antifungal activity was tested against *Aspergillus niger* by cup-plate method. *p*-tolyl, *o*-anisyl, *o*- and *p*-chlorophenylaza derivatives possessed

very good antifungal activity while *m*-tolyl and *m*-chlorophenylaza derivatives were moderately active.

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Chemical Examination of *Daphne oleoides*

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DAPHNE *oleoides* which belongs to the family Thymelaeaceae is highly poisonous. The roots of the plant are purgative while its barks and leaves are used in cutaneous afflictions¹. Literature survey

showed that no systematic chemical investigation of the plant has been done. This prompted us to investigate the plant. The residue obtained from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of crushed dried leaves of *D. oleoides* was taken up in ether and separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was dissolved in pet. ether and adsorbed over a column of silica gel. The pet. ether : benzene (3 : 1) eluate gave a fraction-A, crystallised from pet. ether, mp 83°, $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 332 (OH), 1125, 1075, 1062 and 725 cm^{-1} . It appears to be a fatty alcohol but it was not further characterised. Further elution of the column with pet. ether : benzene (1 : 1) gave fraction B, mp 134-35°. It formed an acetate, mp 131-32°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by comparison (mmp, co-TLC, and IR) with an authentic sample available in the laboratory. Elution of the column with pet. ether : benzene (1 : 2) gave fraction C, mp 184-86°, which formed an acetate, mp 224-25°. It was characterised as a α -amyrin, by comparison (mmp and IR) with an authentic sample. Further elution with benzene gave a fraction D, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M^+426), mp 213°. It gave a pink \rightarrow violet colour

in the Liebermann-Burchard test. Its IR spectrum in Nujol showed bands at 3320 cm^{-1} (OH) and 882 cm^{-1} ($=\text{CH}_2$). The compound on heating with Ac_2O and pyridine furnished an acetate, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ (M^+468), mp 215-16°. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern indicated that the compound may be lupeol. It was finally identified as lupeol by comparison (mmp, co-TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

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